

Recommendations to Improve The Utilization of Dental and Oral Care: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

Background: Analysis the goals of the utilization of dental services at the dental health service is elementary school students who need dental care can keep their teeth as long as possible in their mouth (preventive). The reasons for not fulfilling the utilization of dental services include parents not feeling comfortable when their children visit the Community Health Center, not knowing the importance of dental care for problematic teeth/students' parents not paying attention to the presence of tooth decay and feeling that their children's teeth are still healthy.

Objective: This research aims to compile several recommendations for health services and community health centers that influence the utilization of dental and oral health care in children through systematic review analysis.

Materials and Methods: The analysis method used in descriptive systematic review. The strategy used to search for articles using PICO and literature search was conducted in February 2025. The systematic review uses the PRISMA checklist to determine whether the studies have been reaching out and are similar to the purpose of a systematic review. The total number of studies was fifteen articles.

Result: Factors that can influence the utilization of dental and oral health services in elementary school students are consumer factors, enabling factors, perceived needs, and evaluated needs. Enabling factors are support achieving goals include income, having health insurance, social support and distance. Perceived need, the condition of the disease felt by the individual so that they have a stimulus in using health services. Evaluated need is visiting the dentist after receiving the examination that had been carried out, then given a referral.

Conclusion: The health service and community health centers need to be an active role in providing assistance and supervision to the utilization/use of dental services by providing counseling to the community, collaborating with the private sector through CSR in providing contributions to the community through mobile dental clinic services, Formation of school dental health cadres by providing training and assistance to elementary school students.

KEYWORDS: Utilization, Dental care, Enable Factor, Perceived Need, Recommendation

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I. INTRODUCTION

Efforts to realize a Free-Caries Indonesia will be challenging because dental and oral health problems in Indonesia are still increasing. Based on data from the Indonesian Health Survey (SKI, 2023), the proportion of the population who have not received action/treatment from health workers to overcome their complaints for more than the last 3 years is 90%, the majority who never go to the dentist are children. The rationale for achieving caries-free Indonesia is to strengthen promotive and preventive efforts

from the health center and increase community independence. One of the program from the health center's activities is to provide referrals to students to fulfill the utilization or use of dental care at the health center. The utilization of dental services at the health center dental clinic, one of which has the aim of so that elementary school students who need dental care can maintain their teeth as long as possible in their mouths (preventive) and dental health-promotive efforts in the form of providing education

Recommendations to Improve The Utilization of Dental and Oral Care: A Systematic Review

about dental and oral health, providing leaflets, and educational videos.

The coverage of dental service utilization in elementary school students was obtained by conducting screening/surveys at school. After the screening/survey, dentists or dental nurses no longer conduct dental examinations and tend to wait passively for visits from parents/teachers and students. So it cannot be known whether students who need dental care have utilized dental care in other health services or have not utilized dental services. Students who need dental care, if they do not immediately receive treatment, over time the damage to the teeth and supporting tissue of the teeth will become more severe, may require root canal treatment, or may even result in tooth loss at a young age. So dental care takes more time, and the cost of treatment is increasingly expensive.

Based on an initial survey conducted through interviews with 15 parents of students at an elementary school, the reasons for not fulfilling the utilization of dental services include parents not feeling comfortable when their children visit the health center, not knowing the importance of dental care for problematic teeth/parents of students ignoring the presence of tooth decay and feeling that their children's teeth are still healthy, and children feeling afraid to visit the dentist. The results of observations and interviews with researchers showed that dental health workers at the health center had carried out dental examinations and counseling for all students in January - February. From the periodic examinations, efforts have also been made to collect data and notify teachers for children who need dental care by providing referrals to the health center. However, these efforts were considered unsuccessful because children who needed dental care did not come to utilize dental services at the health center's dental clinic.

Predisposing factors that encourage an individual to use health services include knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, convictions, and perceptions of parents, along with enabling/supporting factors, specifically the accessibility of health facilities/services., affordability, distance, and transportation facilities, and need/need factors. The need factor consists of two perceptions, namely from the consumer side (perceived need) and the health worker side (evaluated need). This is because there are differences in the concept of health or illness between the community and health workers.

The aim of this study was to compile several recommendations for health services and community health centers that influence the utilization of dental and oral health care in children through systematic review analysis.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

A literature search was taken in February 2025. The data is tertiary data obtained from the results of research that has been taken from the previous researchers. The source of tertiary data was obtained from reputable international

sources with the utilization of dental care services in elementary school students. The impact of dental and oral diseases on quality of life is that they can experience dental and oral health problems that cause them to not go to school, or not work, not be able to play (kids), or not be able to do activities. A literature search uses databases of reputable and trusted scientific journals, such as Scopus, Science Direct, PubMed, and Google Scholar. The way of the database is because the journal publisher is accredited and often used by other researchers to search for literature in their research. Arranging the article questions using a PICO (Population/Patient/Problem, Intervention/Indicator, Comparison/Control, Outcomes). PICO in this study are P: elementary school-age children involved to fulfill utilization, I: not applicable, C: not applicable, O: factors that influence children or parents/guardians of children to fulfill utilization as primary outcomes, and caries or gum disorders as secondary outcomes. The article used a qualitative and quantitative study with a cross-sectional assessment of the use of factors that influence elementary school children to never visit the dentist and what recommendations are given to influence elementary school students. Studies were screened by year of publication (2016–2024) and English. The research with qualitative designs, quantitative studies with only univariate analysis or with no statistical analysis, and observational studies in which dental use is allocated as a secondary outcome were excluded.

The process of locating articles or journals by utilizing keywords and boolean operators (AND, OR, NOT, or AND NOT), which are used to expand or specify searches. The literature search used the following text words: ("children dental health" OR "children oral health problem" OR "children dental health problem"). In conducting a study selection, articles deemed unsuitable will be excluded, which will be documented in the selection strategy using PRISMA flowcharts. Subsequently, an analysis will be performed on the selected articles, adhering to the established protocol and eligibility criteria, to ascertain the study results. The Prisma Flowchart shows the process of identifying and choosing eligible studies for the systematic review in Fig 1.

Recommendations to Improve The Utilization of Dental and Oral Care: A Systematic Review

Fig 1. Prisma Flowchart Article The Dental Care Utilization among Children

According to the search of the literature, there are eight articles included that recognized research RCT (Randomized Control Trial) design with a cross-sectional research design with primary data, a total sample (n = 4,130), so secondary data with a total sample (n = 15), originating from India (3), Nigeria (1), the UK (5), Poland (3), New Zealand (2), and China (1). Several articles have explained the research objectives, sample randomization, and sample homogeneity from these studies and can be applied to the local population.

The information gathered from the qualitative research consisted of the article's title and citation, objective, aim, study type, and design. It also contained details regarding obstacles, enablers, access, and delivery of dental care, as well as children's attitudes towards dental appointments

III. RESULT

From the results of the study of fifteen articles conducted in the literature review, all studies reported that the factors that can influence the utilization of dental and oral health services in elementary school students are consumer factors, enabling factors, perceived needs, and evaluated needs.

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Table 1. Summary of Study and Study Results

NO.	Year, Author, Title, Journal	Research Objectives, Research Design, Total Samples	Study Results
1.	2016. Suljana, A., et al. Barriers of Dental Care Utilization for Children Living in Military and Civilian Areas. <i>Journal of the Indian Society of Pedodontics & Preventive Dentistry</i> .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective: To evaluate dental anxiety in 12–15 years old and its correlation with demographic factors, past dental experiences, and child behavior. Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data Sample size: 1522 middle school-aged children 	Dental anxiety is linked to age, gender, type of school, inconsistent dental visit patterns, painful experiences from past dental appointments, and adverse behaviors during dental check-up.
2.	2016. Flores, Glenn et al., <i>A Cross-sectional Study of Parental Awareness of and Reasons for Lack of Health Insurance among Minority Children, and The Impact on Health, Access to Care, and Unmet Needs</i> . International Journal for Equity in Health PubMed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective: To determine the effects on health and healthcare, parental knowledge of uninsured children's eligibility for Medicaid and that's why children lost or never attained health coverage Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data Sample size: 267 participants 	The uninsured children experience poor health, limited access to care, and significant unmet healthcare needs, including mental health services, mobility aids/devices, dental care, specialty healthcare, and vision care. The information further suggests that targeted actions need to be taken for groups most at risk of

Recommendations to Improve The Utilization of Dental and Oral Care: A Systematic Review

			parental unawareness regarding their children's Medicaid eligibility including those uninsured the longest, those at the higher end of income eligibility, and Latinos. ethnic group-specific barriers, which would seem to be crucial to target in efforts to improve the health and healthcare of uninsured minority children.
3.	2017. Lamber, M.J. et al., <i>Socioeconomic Inequalities in Caries Experience, Care Level and Dental Attendance in Primary School Children in Belgium: A Cross-Sectional Survey</i> . BMJ Open Journal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective: To investigate disparities in oral health and evaluate how socioeconomic elements affect the oral health, oral health practices, and dental adherence of primary school students Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data Sample size: 2216 children in 105 primary schools in Flanders 	Children from low-income families do not visit a dentist even once over the span of 5 years. Children's social class negatively influences oral health, oral hygiene, the level of oral healthcare, and dental attendance habits.
4.	2017. Naavaal, S. et al., <i>The Effect of Health and Dental Insurance on US Children's Dental Care Utilization for Urgent and Non-Urgent Dental Problems</i> . Journal of Public Health Dentistry.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective: To assess the use of care for a dental issue and the urgency of dental problems reported by parents for children with dental issues based on the type of health insurance coverage Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data Sample size: A total of 2,834 children, aged 2 to 17 years, reported having at least one dental issue in the six months prior to the survey 	The variation in usage based on the urgency of dental issues was greater for children covered by Medicaid/SCHIP than for those with either PHND or no insurance. The expansion of Medicaid/SCHIP could allow children to access urgent dental care who might not otherwise have it because they lack dental insurance.
5.	2018. Finlayson, T.L. et al., <i>Dental Service Utilization Among Children in the Child Welfare System</i> . Maternal and Child Health Journal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective: To investigate the factors related to predisposition, enablement, and need concerning children's dental usage. Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data Sample size: 2,817 children 	Pediatricians, social workers, and other social service providers can play an important role in promoting oral health education.
6.	2018. Alshoraim, M.A. et al., <i>Effects of Child Characteristics and Dental History on Dental Fear: Cross-Sectional Study</i> . BMC Oral Health.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Objective: To evaluate dental anxiety in Arabic speaking children aged 12–15 in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, and its connection to demographic factors, past dental experiences, and child behavior. Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data Sample size: 522 children of middle school age who were randomly chosen from various schools 	Connections existed between dental anxiety and being female, younger age, attending public schools, seeking dental care only when symptomatic, avoiding the dentist due to fear, experiencing pain in past dental visits, and demonstrating poor behavior during dental assessments. This research highlights the significance of regular dental visits and the application of

Recommendations to Improve The Utilization of Dental and Oral Care: A Systematic Review

			suitable behavioral guidance and efficient pain management during dental procedures to reduce the likelihood of dental anxiety.
7.	2018. Sudan, J. et al., <i>Assessing Clinical Sequelae of Untreated Caries among 5-, 12-, and 15-year-old School Children in Ambala District: A Cross-Sectional Study</i> . Journal of Indian Society of Pedodontics and Preventive Dental.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective: To evaluate the frequency and seriousness of oral issues associated with untreated dental cavities by means of pulp involvement, ulceration, fistula, and abscess index • Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data • Sample size: 433 school children of 5-, 12-, and 15-year-old age group 	The programs for preventing and promoting oral health target young school-age children, their parents, and the broader community by regularly organizing oral health initiatives. Since schools are the microcosm of the larger community with prevailing structures and systems in place provides, an exquisite scope to integrate oral health into school curriculum, and attempts can be made to influence students' oral health knowledge, beliefs, attitudes, and behavior which change the lifestyle.
8.	2018. Mika, A. et al., <i>The Child's First Dental Visit. Age, Reasons, Oral Health Status and Dental Treatment Needs among Children in Southern Poland</i> . European Journal of Paediatric Dentistry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective: To establish the age and reasons for the child's initial dental appointment, and to evaluate the oral health condition and treatment requirements in the examined group of pediatric patients. • Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data • Sample size: 320 children (154 girls and 166 boys) ranging in age from 0.7 months to 13.5 years 	The poor oral hygiene of Polish children during their initial dental appointment and the limited health knowledge of their parents and guardians. There is a pressing requirement to inform parents and guardians of young children about dental prevention and healthy practices.
9.	2020. Cruz, S.P. et al., <i>Oral Health Problems and Utilization of Dental Services among Spanish and Immigrant Children and Adolescents</i> . International Journal Environ Research Public Health.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective: To investigate the frequency of dental issues and the use of dental services, determine the types of treatment provided, and examine the socioeconomic and demographic factors linked to dental problems and irregular use of dental care services. • Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data • Sample size: 4568 children aged between 3 and 14 years old 	The type of dental appointment most frequently scheduled by children is for a check-up. The likelihood of irregular use of dental services is reduced in Spanish and immigrant children aged 7 and older, rising as social class declines. Furthermore, the probability of experiencing dental health issues increases in both groups starting at age 7 and among those in the lower social class.
10.	2022. Alanzi, Abrar et al., <i>Pediatricians Knowledge of Children's Oral Health: A National Survey</i> . International Dental Journal.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective: To assess the understanding and awareness of pediatricians and pediatric residents about children's oral health in Kuwait 	Inadequate awareness regarding the preventive strategies for dental caries and dental injuries has been recorded among

Recommendations to Improve The Utilization of Dental and Oral Care: A Systematic Review

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data • Sample size: 230 participants 	<p>paediatricians. Nevertheless, they possessed sufficient knowledge regarding the present anticipatory guidance related to children's oral health. Numerous paediatricians were eager to conduct suitable oral evaluations, provide dental referrals, and administer fluoride varnish. Ongoing oral health education courses are necessary to guarantee excellent care for children both locally and globally.</p>
11.	2022. Hussein, T.O. et al., <i>Management of Post-Traumatic Dental Care Anxiety in Pediatric Dental Practice</i> . MDPI Journals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective: To assess if non-pharmacological behavior management techniques can successfully lower the reliance on pharmacological behavior management in children experiencing Post-Traumatic Dental care Anxiety (PTDA) who are referred for routine dental treatments under general anesthesia and sedation. • Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data • Sample size: 20 healthy children aged 4–14 	<p>This clinical study revealed that children experiencing post-traumatic dental care anxiety could be retrained and managed through non-pharmacological behavior techniques procedures. Behavioral (non-pharmaceutical) management who reduced the need for dental treatment under general anesthesia in three-quarters of patients between two and six appointments.</p>
12.	2022. Trinh, M.V. et al., <i>Dental Visits in Early Life: Patterns and Barriers among Australian Children</i> . Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective: To identify the early patterns of dental service usage among children in Australia and examine obstacles to obtaining care. • Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data • Sample size: A total 2,048 parents of 3,660 children 	<p>Parents belief that children are too young for their first dental visit at 12 months leads to lost chances for prevention, detection, and early intervention to decrease the seriousness and advancement of oral disease. Cooperation among all health professionals who frequently interact with children prior to their initial visit can tackle the deficit in oral health knowledge, support early referrals to dental experts, and strengthen health-promoting behaviors.</p>
13.	2023. Jimenez, C.C. et al., <i>Relationship between Children's Lifestyle and Fear during Dental Visits: A Cross-Sectional Study</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective: to examine the connection between emerging family and social trends and children's feelings in the dental office • Methods: cross-sectional study, primary data • Sample size: 174 children 	<p>The family significantly affects the child's cognitive, personal, emotional, and social-emotional growth. Kids who don't sleep properly may experience health issues and behavioral problems.</p>

Recommendations to Improve The Utilization of Dental and Oral Care: A Systematic Review

14.	2023. Kumar et al., <i>Oral Health of Women and Children: Progress, Challenges, and Priorities</i> . Maternal and Child Health Journal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective: to improved oral significantly more actions are required to enhance oral health and offer early • Methods: Review paper • Sample size: - 	The health-related social and commercial factors must be tackled. The divide between dentistry and general health care has resulted in oral health care financing and delivery systems that restrict access to treatment and sustain inequalities in oral health.
15.	2024. Mashaddani et al., <i>Barriers and Facilitators to Dental Care Services Utilization Among Children With Disabilities: A Systematic Review and Thematic Synthesisi</i> . Health Expectation Journal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective: to improved enhance oral health and offer early • Methods: Review paper • Sample size: - 	Effective communication became essential, as dental providers highlighted the need to comprehend the circumstances of both the child and parents, along with gathering thorough information regarding the child's condition prior to appointments to enable better treatment planning.

Consumer factors, the population is mostly parents/communities with a predominantly lower middle education level. Then, enabling factors, income level and time are variables that are often found as obstacles to fulfilling dental service utilization. Perceived need, evaluated need is the most frequently found variable but there are still many obstacles that have not been resolved. In the relationship analysis, 9 articles were found, stating that there is a relationship between consumer factors, namely the feeling of discomfort in visiting the dentist, and the utilization of dental services

IV. DISCUSSIONS

This systematic review looks into existing literature to examine the factors affecting the oral healthcare of children with disabilities from a qualitative perspective. The review resulted in five themes related to stereotypes in dental care, communication between dental providers and parents, training to address gaps in dental management, sustainable oral health education and establishing dental-medical collaboration.

Consumer Factors are sociodemographic, sociopsychological, epidemiological. Demographic factors are divided into two groups, namely gender and age. Based on the results of the literature review, it was obtained that girls, and children over 6 years of age and public school students were significantly more afraid of utilizing dental services than boys, older children, and private school children. The girls when they were 9 years old showed an increase in the use of dental services, namely 49.9% (Miriam Del et al., 2017). The mothers aged 35 years and over, the frequency of examinations was significantly higher compared to younger mothers. High maternal education

level will affect the utilization of dental services for their children. A mother with a high education will take preventive measures and reduce symptoms or symptomatic actions in her children by utilizing dental services. Retired parents, and unemployed parents are twice as likely to take their children to the dentist compared to children of managers and professional parents, due to the inability of parents to provide time. Working parents consider fulfilling dental service utilization to cut working hours when using health services (Flores et al., 2016). The efficacy of perceived needs and the efficacy of dental care is a strong reason for preventive medical visits to the dentist (Naavaal et al., 2017).

Enabling factors are support achieving goals include income, having health insurance, social support and distance. Half of children with low-income parents were able to utilize regular dental visits while 12.6% had no dental visits during the past 5-year period. Children with middle- and high-income parents visited the dentist more regularly (77.7%). Only 3.4% of these children did not report any dental visits (Martijn et al., 2017). Mothers whose children are insured are more likely to utilize dental care for their children. There is a significant increase in insurance utilization among those with low education, compared to uninsured households, but not among those with higher education levels (Medina-Solis et al., 2019). However, parents who are uninsured, or have financial difficulties, difficulty paying for care, are less likely to utilize dental services.

Perceived need, the condition of the disease felt by the individual so that they have a stimulus in using health services. The main reason for fulfilling utilization is because the patient feels a toothache and wants to have a tooth

Recommendations to Improve The Utilization of Dental and Oral Care: A Systematic Review

extracted. Previous experiences of toothache/caries increase the likelihood of visiting the dentist. Children with unmet needs who are unable to get treatment have a low perception of pain, so the chances of using dental services are lower (Tracy *et al.*, 2018). Children who have a higher fear of dental care are children who have not visited the dentist in the past year or those who only visit the dentist when sick or have refused during previous dental visits. Evaluated need, visiting the dentist after receiving the examination that had been carried out, then given a referral because the parent/caregiver wanted to fulfill the child's request (41.6%) to visit the dental clinic

V. CONCLUSIONS

Several factors that can increase elementary school students to utilize dental care to health services are need characteristics, especially evaluated need, the factor of a person's need for health services is the most important factor compared to other factors in service utilization, then education level, income, parents' occupation, ownership of health insurance, and time. The recommendations given to the health service and community health centers are: (1) It is expected to have an active role in providing assistance and supervision to the utilization/use of dental services by providing counseling to the community to provide knowledge regarding the utilization/use of dental services, especially to people with lower secondary education levels; (2) The Health Service and Community Health Centers can also collaborate with the private sector through "Corporate Social Responsibility" is contributing to the community through mobile dental clinic services, (3) Formation of school dental health cadres by providing training and mentoring for elementary school students (Training of Trainer) to always motivate elementary school students to visit the dentist.

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